

AXIOLOGICAL PARAMETRES OF SPEECH ACTS WITH THE EXPLICIT MODE OF IGNORANCE IN SCIENTIFIC DIALOGUE

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on speech acts with the mode of ignorance and its axiological parametres in scientific dialogue (in English). The paper discusses the factors making axiological speech acts with the mode of ignorance function in dialogical scientific communication. It also identifies the main classes of speech acts of this type (depending on the shades of meaning they transmit). The conclusion about the pragmatic role of speech acts with the mode of ignorance represented in scientific dialogue is made.

Keywords: scientific discourse, scientific dialogue, epistemic components, epistemic modifications, mode of ignorance, speech act, pragmatic features.

INTRODUCTION

Discourse as a complex and dynamic communicative phenomenon has recently been a rather popular object of linguistic research and humanitarian analysis in general [1–8, etc.].

A special type of discourse is scientific discourse which is one of the least understood types of discourse today.

A unique variety of scientific discourse is scientific dialogue. It differs from the other genres of scientific communication in many ways. One of its main distinctions (in comparison with other forms of scientific discourse) is its specific epistemic organization. As is widely known, the major components of the epistemic structure of scientific communication is knowledge and opinion / supposition. However, the spontaneous and expressive character of scientific dialogue (that can develop at a scientific forum of any format, e. g. scientific conference, seminar, panel discussion, etc.) makes it a unique communicative event the parameters of which can change. Its epistemic parametres are no exception. They can be modified in the following way: peripheral epistemic components of the scientific discourse system can be activated. One of these epistemic components is ignorance.

Ignorance is opposed to knowledge and is usually represented in scientific speech through references to areas and phenomena that are a blind spot in science and should be carefully studied (these references are typically found at the beginning of a scientific paper – at the stage of formulating the objectives of the research, or at the end of the paper – at the stage of appealing to the perspectives of the project). However, in scientific dialogue, ignorance can also be manifested in speech acts with the explicit mode of ignorance, i. e. don't-know-constructions (*I / We don't know...*, etc.):

Now, before you think this is a trivial matter, remember, in many cases these therapists or researchers do not know who is behind the avatar.

As is clearly seen, the don't-know-constructions are not at all discreditable towards the subject of ignorance (*these therapists and researchers*) and aim at fulfilling some pragmatic functions, to be more exact – the function of warning. Thus, their use in scientific speech is often justified by their important communicative role and usually doesn't damage the speaker's reputation.

As our data show, pragmatic functions of don't-know-speech-acts can be different. One of them is the axiological function, which is about showing a speaker's attitude (usually negative) towards something or someone. In this paper, we are going to focus on the functional aspects of axiological speech acts with the mode of ignorance. The importance to set an objective like that is predetermined by the necessity to study the problem of a proper interpretation of the epistemic assessment of the sentence proposition (the objective part of the sentence). **The methods** of contextual, pragmalinguistic and transformational analysis have been used. **The research material** is represented by transcripts of modern scientific discussions (in English) in different disciplinary spheres: Medicine, Ethics, Maths / Science, etc.

MAIN PART

As already been said, most axiological speech acts with the mode of ignorance are of negative character. A **negatively-marked don't-know-speech-act** is an utterance that demonstrates somebody's unfavourable attitude towards somebody's position, words, views, opinions, behavior, etc., give a negative assessment of a state of affairs. Axiological don't-know-speech-acts can be of several **types** depending on the shades of meaning they transmit:

- disagreement,
- objection,
- doubt,
- negative characteristic,
- regret,
- complaint.

Our further discussion is about the main types of negatively-marked don't-know-speech-acts functioning in scientific dialogue.

1. Disagreement / objection

This type of negatively-marked don't-know-construction can be illustrated by means of the following speech episode, e. g.:

(1): *Would it be fair to say that that depth of content increases as you go up through the grades? Is that a fair assessment? Elementary teachers with the least? Professors with the most? Is that a reasonable assessment?* – (2): **I don't know** that is true. *I am not sure I would agree with that.*

The first speaker suggests the idea of the dependence of a teacher's proficiency on the status of the teacher, which causes the interlocutor's negative reaction to the concept. Although the interlocutor doesn't express his unfavourable attitude towards the suggested idea directly (instead of saying *That's not true. I disagree with that*, the speaker prefers to transform this statement about disagreement into a don't-know-phrase for this purpose), which reduces the polemic effect of his words, his message is still to be interpreted as disagreement as it shows a lack of consensus on the issue discussed.

A case of objection can be found in the context below:

Well, I don't disagree with that if you make a whole organism, but we don't know that you can make an organism, and moreover, I've made it very clear that both personally and in terms of the COSEPP report, we believe that trying to do that should be banned. No question.

The speaker specifies his communicative intention by qualifying it as not a disagreement (*I don't disagree with that*). Nevertheless, his so-called "agreement" is far from being unconditional (*if you make a whole organism*). The speaker's words obviously contain some elements of protest and correction as well as the elements of explanation, which makes the don't-know-construction sound as an objection. Besides, the expressive and highly categorical part *No question* only adds to this effect and emphasizes the axiological character of the speech act with the mode of ignorance.

2. Critical comment / regret / complaint

Sometimes, it's a challenging task to identify the real intention of the author of the axiological don't-know speech act. It can be treated as either regret (feeling sorrow for some state of affairs) or complaint (expressing dissatisfaction about something), etc. There is a very thin line between these notions. What is evident is the presence of the negative (critical) component in the semantic structure of the don't-know-speech-act, as can be seen in the example below:

I think that a lot of what happens is that the teacher may not know – may think that this is a wonderful activity, but they don't know how to engage the common discourse that happens after the activity, before the activity and during the activity <...>.

On the one hand, the part *They don't know how to engage the common discourse that happens after the activity, before the activity and during the activity* may seem to be just an ordinary statement which is empty of any elements of a negative assessment. However, a closer look at the context helps us see the speaker's true attitude towards the situation and his wishing an imaginary teacher to behave differently, to be able to arrange the activity under consideration in a proper way, which proves the don't-know-speech-act to be of axiological (negatively-marked) character. This negative effect is produced through using the tactics of indirect comparison / opposition of two situations (realities) the first of which (the ideal situation) is labelled with the qualitative adjective *wonderful* (*this is a wonderful activity*), while the other (the reality) is marked with the help of the conjunction *but* and the don't-know-construction

(*but they don't know how to engage the common discourse*). This very opposition implies the speaker's being skeptical about the idea suggested.

It should be noted that don't-know-constructions of regret / complaint functioning in scientific dialogue are often of emotional character as they usually contain emotionally-coloured vocabulary (as a rule, adjectives), e. g.:

Let me give an example of that based on the fact that the current in a circuit is the derivative of voltage. A common problem in electrical engineering texts is: Here's the graph of the voltage in a circuit; sketch the graph of the current. It's amazing how many students, who have completed a full three semesters of calculus, have no idea where to begin. All they can do is differentiate any conceivable expression, but they don't know what it means.

The use of the emotional adjective *amazing* does not only emphasize the expressive background of the conversation and demonstrates the speaker's surprise but also serves (together with the speech act with the mode of ignorance *but they don't know what it means*) as a means of expressing his negative attitude to the fact of students' inability to sketch the graph of the current. Thus, a combination of emotionally-marked lexemes with don't-know-constructions (as well as with the tactics of comparison / opposition) is a common way to leave a critical comment in scientific dialogue, a universal feature of negatively marked contexts of critical comment / regret / complaint about the current state of affairs (cf.: *There is a tremendous amount of stuff we don't know, but we do have a good start in terms of the science of learning*).

3. Doubt / negative characteristic

The elements of doubt can be found in different axiological don't-know-constructions including those considered above (like in the statement *I don't know that is true. I am not sure I would agree with that* that has recently been analyzed and the author of which isn't certain about the suggested idea as well as about his disagreement).

Speech acts marked for doubt and expressing some negative attitude can be of the reflexive and metalinguistic character, which means that they can focus on the message of the author himself / herself and characterize this message as appropriate or inappropriate.

I don't know if that is the right question. If it is not, we can skip it, but you mentioned that ideas follow logically from one to another.

In this very context, the author is not sure of whether his question is appropriate or inappropriate (*I don't know if that is the right question*), thus characterizing it in a negative (discrediting) way. Of course, this negative characteristic is quite formal as it hardly deprives the question of the right to be raised. In fact, the statement *I don't know if that is the right question* serves as a means of minimizing a potentially nagging nature of the question.

Thus, axiological don't-know-constructions function as an important pragmatic phenomenon that expresses different shades of the speaker's negative attitude towards something in scientific dialogue.

It should be mentioned that axiological speech acts with the mode of ignorance can be not only negative but also *positive* (positive axiological don't-know acts are about praising someone or agreeing with something). However, positive don't-know-constructions are just a few in dialogical scientific discourse, which can probably be explained by a more important role of a negative (rather than positive) assessment in scientific discourse – only the negative assessment (formulated in a tolerant way) can promote the development of science in general and scientific speech in particular, e. g.:

Yes, I don't know of any other book that does it the way this book does it, in such a clear, thorough way.

The message above is an appeal to a false (not true) ignorance as it rather stresses the uniqueness of the book than informs about a lack of knowledge. The statement acquires axiological traits through qualifying the book as clear and thorough (*this book does it, in such a clear, thorough way*).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Don't-know-constructions can never be found in any other type of scientific discourse (at least in the nuclear / central genres of scientific communication: article, monograph, thesis, etc.), while their use in scientific dialogue is predetermined by the specific features of the latter: spontaneous (relatively free) and expressive character as well as emotional, dialogic, and polemic nature.

2. In spite of quite a number of varieties of axiological don't-know-constructions (those expressing disagreement, objection, doubt, regret, etc.), their occurrence in scientific dialogue is limited by both G. P. Grice's cooperative maxims (quality, quantity, relevance, and manner) and norms and standards of institutional communication.

3. Although axiological don't-know-constructions show the speaker's lack of knowledge in some sphere, they never undermine his / her professional status, but at the same time, they discredit the interlocutor in some

way as they show the negative attitude towards his / her ideas and suggestions.

Axiological role is not the only pragmatic load of don't-know-constructions represented in English scientific discourse. They can perform a variety of different communicative tasks in the text varying from interrogative speech acts to directive utterances either of which can become a perspective and promising research object in linguistics.

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